

THE APPLICATION OF MODIFIED ACTIVITIES IN THE PRACTICE OF TEACHING OF ENGLISH AS FOREIGN (SECOND) LANGUAGE FOR STUDENTS OF NON-LINGUISTIC HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

Through many years, teaching and learning English as a second or foreign language have been undergone through various methods, and thus linguists have been tried to incorporate these diverse methods and techniques in learning processes based on the principles of language learning and teaching. Nevertheless, linguists have been witnessed that there is no ultimate method or techniques, which could be applied in every teaching context. However, the prime aim of language teaching is to prepare the learners to apply target language in real-life contexts. Taking into account the above-mentioned insights the aim of the current article is to present two diverse modified activities, which are developed in accordance to Communicative Language Teaching methods.

Key words: post era method, Communicative Language Teaching, working collaboratively, student-centered classrooms, teacher-centered classroom, modified activity.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ МОДИФИЦИРОВАННЫХ РАЗРАБОТКА ВИДОВ УЧЕБНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СТУДЕНТАМИ НЕЯЗЫКОВЫХ ВУЗОВ В ПРАКТИКЕ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА КАК ИНОСТРАННОГО (КАК ВТОРОГО)

Абстракт

На протяжении многих лет преподавание и изучение английского языка как второго (иностранного) осуществлялось с помощью различных методов. Включение различных методов и приемов в процесс обучения основано на принципах изучения и преподавания английского языка как иностранного. По мнению лингвистов, не существует окончательного метода или техники, которые можно было бы применять в любом контексте обучения. Основная цель обучения языку состоит в том, чтобы подготовить студентов к применению изучаемого языка в реальных условиях. Цель данной статьи состоит в том, чтобы в рамках коммуникативного метода показать модифицированную версию двух различных видов и их использование в практике преподавания английского языка как иностранного (второго).

Ключевые слова: английский язык как иностранный, коммуникативный метод, работа в малых группах, разработка видов учебной деятельности, фокус внимания на учителе (на студенте).

As Brown (2002) mentioned that "A glance at the history of language teaching reveals some interesting "changing winds and shifting sand." If some of them is considered the extent to which methodological trends have been emphasized the roles of teacher and the learner. Most of language teaching methodology was teacher-centered, however in the 1970s some of the "designer" methods appeared and the educational profession commenced to emphasize the value of learner autonomy in the form of learner-centered approaches. In spite of developing wide range methods in teaching language, the problem is that none of them could actually provide teachers with ultimate way of teaching their students. The question is here why? The reason is learners are different, cultures are different, societies are different. Moreover, within a specific context, there is also plenty of

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diversity (age, gender, social class, ethnicity etc.). Taking into consideration all the language teaching domain faced with denial of the idea that a specific method is better than the others, and the era which is called and coined by Kumarevadeveli "post era method" appeared.

As we are now post era method teachers are considered to create their own methods and approaches concerning to all previous methods and approaches as well. According to the principles of the post era methods lesson should be conducted as student-centered rather than teacher-centered. As Brown (2002) states that "classroom teachers do best when they ground their pedagogy in well-established principles of language teaching and learning". Moreover, Kumaravadivelu (1994) suggests a framework, which contains 10 macro strategies (maximize learning opportunities, facilitate negotiated interaction, minimize perceptual mismatches, activate intuitive heuristics, foster language awareness, contextualize linguistic input, integrate language skills, promote learner autonomy, ensuring social relevance, raise cultural consciousness). These macro strategies lead the teachers to approach lessons learner-centered and teachers are considered to be facilitators.

The activity is called "listen, fill and make a story" in this activity students begin working individually completing their performance working in groups. This activity is concerned with music, because of the interest of students to listening English songs. Taking advantage of their interest and encourage them working collaboratively. Furthermore, the activity is applied in order to create friendly atmosphere in class. The students will fill the song lyric by listening to it, then using those words or phrases and working with groups the make a story using them as well as linking words such as 'and, but, because, so, although, however'. By doing this activity students will enhance their one of the cores listening skills such as "listening for details", furthermore writing and composition skills will be reinforced as well.

The process of the activity as follows:

ACTIVITY #1. LISTEN, FILL, MAKE A STORY

Original version: Listen to the song and fill the gaps

Original version of this activity is based on the song. The teacher chooses a song appropriately to his/her class level and their students' interests. Then some phrases and words are removed from the lyrics. While listening to the song students fill missed part of the song

Modified Version:

The teacher prepares the lyrics of the song with missing part or gaps (approximately 10 words can be removed including some phrases) and apart that teacher changes five paronyms such as 'live leave, sun- son,' etc.

Then students listen to it and fill the gaps. The next stage learners list the words which they have filled and try to find five incorrect words from the lyrics.

Then discuss as a whole class why those words are not suitable for the lyrics by the meaning and thus, they practice some sounds. Accordingly, the number of students the teacher splits them up into groups of 3 or five members. In the next part, students work in their group and using those ten words and linking words "and, but, because, however, so, although" make their stories. Finally, each group retells stories which they have created.

Target group: elementary intermediate.

Aimed skills and course: this activity is mainly consolidates listening, writing and speaking skills in General English classes.

Directions for the Students:

1. Each student listens to the song attentively

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2. Students fill the gaps in the lyrics
3. Learners list every word or phrase which they have filled
4. Students find five paronyms in the lyrics
5. Learners start to discuss the meaning of the paronym words
6. Students work in groups and write their stories using the words and phrases and linking words 'and, but, because, however, although'

7. Each group reads their stories.

Instruction to the teacher:

1. Pick up lyrics of a song which is more appropriate to student's level.
2. Remove about ten words or phrases and change five original words with their paronyms.
3. Distribute prepared lyrics to students and explain them that they will fill the gaps by listening to the song.
4. Play the music and ask the learners to begin completing the lyrics.
5. After listening to the song ask the target students to list the words and phrases they have found while listening to the song.
6. Tell students to find five changed words in the lyrics and discuss their meaning.
7. Split the learners up into groups of three or four members and tell them to create their own group stories based on any topic they would like to speak using the words and linking words 'and, but, because, however, although'.
8. Outline that students are considered to use linking words appropriately while they are making stories.
9. Ask each group to present their stories.

Assessment

Assessment will be held in the following way:

The content and accuracy of the story, and appropriate usage of the linking words. The group which creates the funniest story and uses linking words correctly will be considered as a winner.

The further activity is "the text jigsaw" which is taken and adapted from "Teaching Large Multi-Level Classes" written by Natalie Hess (2001). The jigsaw reading is a popular activity among many educators and the current activity encourages students to communicate with each other and consolidates learners' summarizing skills. As Scarcella, Anderson, & Krashen (1990) outlines that "To develop communicative abilities, learners need to experience or practice communicating in the language they are learning by negotiating meanings with others" and 'the text jigsaw' is a really good activity to meet these demands. In a modified version of this activity students' communication, group working, critical thinking, summarizing, presenting skills will be considered to be improved. The process of the activity as follows:

ACTIVITY #2 THE TEXT JIGSAW

Original version:

The teacher brings authentic text and cut it into four sections and copies each section and distributes the copies and tells each student to read their sections attentively and students share their sections with each other and put parts of the stories in order.

Modified version:

The teacher brings three different reading materials to the class and divides each reading text into three sections and splits students into three groups and distributes one cut text to the one group thus each three groups will have their own cut reading text. Each student in the group reads their own

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sections attentively and each group puts their own text together. Then each group discusses their own text. The teacher provides posters for each group. Students in their group draw the picture in order to show their understanding of text and each group makes their own posters according to the text. At final stage groups presents their posters to the class.

Target group: Pre-intermediate- upper- intermediate

Aimed skills and course: the following activity can be implemented to the General English classes. The goal of this activity is to reinforce reading, explaining, fluency, listening, summarizing and presentation skills of students. Furthermore, it encourages students to work in groups interactively.

Directions to the students:

1. Work in your group and read the piece of your text attentively.
2. Retell and explain your reading section neatly to your group members
3. With the group members gather all parts of the text and put them together in order to make the text as whole.
4. Draw a picture about your information in the reading material, (remember that you are not allowed to use any words) and make poster with your group members about your text.
5. Present your poster to the class.

Instruction to the teacher:

1. Find three different reading materials which are related to one topic. (e.g., three extraordinary restaurants).
2. Cut each reading text into three parts.
3. Divide the students into three groups of three members.
4. Distribute separated reading material to each group members.
5. Explain that the learners are going to read one reading text with their group, but each student reads his/her own part of the text.
6. Tell the students after reading their part they should explain and retell it to their group members and order the sequence of their text and make piece of reading as a whole text.
7. Explain the target groups that they should depict their understanding of the reading material with the help of drawing and tell them to draw picture and make posters.
8. Tell the group that they should present their posters to the class.

Assessment:

Students will be assessed according to their performance in the group The group will be graded according to their presentation of their posters.

CONCLUSION. In spite of the fact that we now in post era method, every educator every class, every education setting does their activities based on their assumption, believes and theoretical principles of learning and teaching languages.

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